

Cauchy Problem for a Semilinear Nonstrictly Hyperbolic Equation on a Half-Plane in the Case of a Single Characteristic

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In the upper half-plane, we consider a semilinear nonstrictly hyperbolic partial differential equation of the n^{th} -order, which arises in modeling of wave propagation in a layered medium, in the study of k -out-of- n systems, in classical field theory. The equation has a single characteristic with a multiplicity equal to n . The operator in the equation is a sum of linear and nonlinear parts. The linear part of this operator is a composition of the first-order differential operator with constant coefficients. The nonlinear part depends on independent variables and unknown function. The equation is equipped with the Cauchy conditions. We find the solution of this problem in the upper half-plane in an implicit analytical form in the case of two independent variables under some smoothness conditions on the initial data, the right-hand side, and nonlinearity, and sign and growth conditions on the nonlinearity.

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1. Introduction

This article continues our studies of the Cauchy problem for linear [1–3] and nonlinear [4–8] hyperbolic equations.

In this paper, we obtain an implicit analytic form of the solution of the Cauchy problem for a n^{th} -order nonlinear nonstrictly hyperbolic equation, where n is a positive integer. The operator in the equation is a sum of linear and nonlinear parts. The linear part of this

operator is a composition of the first-order differential operator with constant coefficients. In the Cauchy problem, the unknown function depends on two independent variables. Using the method proposed in the book [9], and the results of the paper [2], we derive the integral equation for the classical solution of the Cauchy problem. In the case of Lipschitz nonlinearities, we use the Leray–Schauder fixed point theorem [10] to prove global solvability of this integral equation. We establish a uniqueness theorem using the mean value theorem for a wide class of nonlinearities. We also study the Cauchy problem for the partial differential equation by reducing it to the Cauchy problem for an ordinary differential equation. It allows us to study the problem in the case of non-Lipschitz nonlinearities (e.g., power-law ones).

On the one hand, the theory of the Cauchy problem for linear differential hyperbolic

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equations and systems is well developed [9, 11]. On the other hand, the theory of the Cauchy problem for nonlinear equations cannot be considered as constructed and complete. Many results on the existence and nonexistence, uniqueness and nonuniqueness of the classical solutions in it have been obtained only locally and/or for certain cases [9, 11–15]. Usually, when studying problems for nonlinear hyperbolic equations, we have two main choices: 1) growth of the initial data is not bounded, but nonlinearities must satisfy some inequalities that limit their growth; 2) nonlinearities can be of arbitrary growth, but initial data should be bounded by inequalities. There is also the third choice, where we “weaken” the definition of the solution, allowing singularities.

In our research [4, 5, 16] and the present paper, we follow the first option, i.e., we do not assume that the initial data of the problem are infinitely differentiable and/or small but assume that they are sufficiently smooth, namely, from the classes C^m , $m = 1, \dots, n$. We also note that the second approach is used in the papers [17, 18], and the paper [19] deals with the third one.

The paper is organized as follows. Sec. 2 presents auxiliary material for the rest of the article. Sec. 3 contains a statement of the Cauchy problem. In Sec. 4, we reduce the initial value problem to the solution of an integral equation and prove its solvability, uniqueness, and well-posedness. In Sec. 5, we formulate the existence and uniqueness theorem for the Cauchy problem when the nonlinearity satisfies the Lipschitz condition. In Sec. 6, we prove the uniqueness theorem for a wide class of nonlinearities. In Sec. 7, we propose another way to solve the Cauchy problem is proposed by reduction to an ordinary differential equation. In Sec. 8, we talk about mild solutions of the Cauchy problem and prove their existence and uniqueness. Sec. 9 examines some cases of the equation when it is of second order. Sec. 10 considers nonnegative nonlinearities for the equation of order greater than two. Sec. 11 presents the conclusions of the work done.

2. Preliminaries and notation

This section introduces auxiliary notation and statements for the rest of the article.

2.1. Geometry and topology. We denote the convex hull of a set Ω as $\text{Conv}(\Omega)$, the interior of a set Ω as $\text{int}(\Omega)$, the closure of a set Ω as $\bar{\Omega}$, the boundary of a set Ω as $\partial\Omega$.

2.2. Derivatives and differential operators. To be concise, we use the following notation for partial derivatives: $\partial_t = \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$, $\partial_t^2 = \partial_{tt} = \frac{\partial^2}{\partial t^2}$. Let D and D^j be the operators of the first derivative and the j^{th} order derivative, respectively.

2.3. Functional spaces. Let $C^k(\Omega)$ be the set of all k times continuously differentiable functions on Ω , let $C^0(\Omega) = C(\Omega)$ be the set of all continuous functions on Ω . Let $\mathcal{B}_{\text{loc}}(\Omega)$ be the set of all bounded and Lebesgue integrable functions on an arbitrary compact set $\mathcal{K} \subseteq \Omega$.

3. Statement of the problem

In the domain $Q = (0, \infty) \times \mathbb{R}$, consider the m^{th} -order nonlinear differential equation

$$(\partial_t - a\partial_x + b)^m u(t, x) - f(t, x, u(t, x)) = F(t, x), \quad (1)$$

where a and b are given real numbers, satisfying the condition $a \neq 0$ (it means that the line $t = 0$ is not the characteristic of Eq. (1)), F is a function given on the set \bar{Q} , and f is a function given on the set $\bar{Q} \times \mathbb{R}$.

Equation (1) is equipped with the initial condition

$$\partial_t^j u(0, x) = \varphi^{(j)}(x), \quad j = 0, \dots, m-1, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2)$$

where $\varphi^{(j)}$ are functions given on the real axis.

In the linear case, i.e., $f \equiv 0$, the problem (1) – (2) was studied in the classes of sufficiently smooth functions in the work [2] by the method of characteristics. We note that its solution was implemented symbolically with the use of computer algebra systems [20, 21].

In the papers [22, 23] the well-posedness of the linear Cauchy problem (1) – (2) in the C^∞ and Gevrey spaces, respectively, was analyzed. It should be mentioned that the general theory of the correctness of the Cauchy problem for the homogeneous linear equation (1) (i.e., $f \equiv 0$ and $F \equiv 0$) was constructed in the book [24]. Also, generalized solutions and their properties were studied [25, 26] for the problem (1) – (2). Solutions of a similar Cauchy problem with variable infinitely differentiable coefficients in the linear case were constructed in the works [27–30]. However, in these works, some restrictions on the multiplicity of the characteristics were introduced, and/or the initial condition was rapidly oscillating and decaying. Some works, e.g., [31], are devoted to the study of singularities of solutions of the Cauchy problem (1) – (2). Some methods of solving the nonlinear problem (1) – (2) are described in the book [32]. However, it only suggests approaches to obtain a solution to the problem (1) – (2) without giving any assertions about the global and local solvability and the necessary and sufficient smoothness conditions. Therefore, based on the above, the initial value problem (1) – (2) cannot be considered solved.

Eq. (1) describes a wavefield resulting from

the superposition of m waves traveling in one direction with equal velocity. When $m = 1$, Eq. (1) is called the one-dimensional transport equation. Equations of the kind (1) appear in many physical phenomena where discontinuous or singular entities are involved, for instance, in the wave propagation in a layered medium [33]. Eq. (1) is also used for the modeling k -out-of- n systems [34]. In more detail, consider an example from field theory.

Example 2. Consider the following Lagrangian density

$$\mathcal{L}[\phi] = \frac{1}{2} \left((\partial_t \phi)^2 + a^2 (\partial_x \phi)^2 \right) - 2a \partial_t \phi \partial_x \phi + V(\phi),$$

where $\phi = \phi(t, x)$ is a scalar field. This Lagrangian density leads to the following equation of motion

$$(\partial_t - a\partial_x)^2 \phi(t, x) - V'(\phi(t, x)) = 0.$$

From this example, we conclude that Eq. (1) can have some applications in classical field theory.

4. Integral equation

Introduce into consideration the operator K acting by the formula

$$K[u](t, x) = w(t, x) + \frac{1}{(m-1)!} \int_0^t \exp(-b(t-\tau))(t-\tau)^{m-1} \times (F(\tau, x + a(t-\tau)) - f(\tau, x + a(t-\tau), u(\tau, x + a(t-\tau)))) d\tau. \tag{3}$$

where w is a solution of the problem

$$\begin{cases} (\partial_t - a\partial_x + b)^m w(t, x) = 0, & (t, x) \in Q, \\ \partial_t^j w(0, x) = \varphi^{(j)}(x), j = 0, \dots, m-1, & x \in \mathbb{R}. \end{cases} \tag{4}$$

The exact form of the function w does not matter, but it will be specified in the Sec. 8. Here we note only that the function w is well defined, if, for example, $\varphi^{(j)} \in C^{m-j-1}(\mathbb{R})$. Furthermore, the function w belongs to the class $C^m(\mathbb{R})$, i.e.,

it is a classical solution of the problem (4), if $\varphi^{(j)} \in C^{2m-j-1}(\mathbb{R})$.

Theorem 1 *Let the conditions $f \in C^{0,m,m}(\overline{Q}) \times \mathbb{R}$, $F \in C^{0,m,m}(\overline{Q})$, $\varphi \in C^{2m-j-1}(\mathbb{R})$, $j = 0, \dots, m-1$ be satisfied. The function u belongs to the class $C^m(\overline{Q})$ and satisfies Eq. (1) in \overline{Q} and the Cauchy conditions (2) in \mathbb{R} if and only if it is a continuous solution of Eq. (3) in \overline{Q} .*

PROOF

1. We are looking for a solution u of the form $u = w + v$, where w solves (4), and v solves

$$\begin{cases} (\partial_t - a\partial_x + b)^m v(t, x) = F(t, x) \\ + f(t, x, (v + w)(t, x)), (t, x) \in Q, \\ \partial_t^j v(0, x) = 0, j = 0, \dots, m - 1, x \in \mathbb{R}, \end{cases}$$

$$u(t, x) = w(t, x) + \frac{1}{(m - 1)!} \int_0^t \exp(-b(t - \tau))(t - \tau)^{m-1} \times \\ \times (F(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)) - f(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), u(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)))) d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \overline{Q}.$$

Thus, our desired solution u must solve the nonlinear integral identity (3).

2. If the function u is a continuous solution of Eq. (3) then, by virtue of the smoothness conditions $f \in C^{0,m,m}(\overline{Q} \times \mathbb{R})$, $F \in C^{0,m,m}(\overline{Q})$, and $\varphi \in C^{2m-j-1}(\mathbb{R})$ ($j = 1, \dots, n$), similarly to the works [35, 36], we can increase the smoothness of u to $C^m(\mathbb{R})$. Substituting the representations (3) into Eq. (1) and the initial conditions (2), we verify that the function u satisfies them in \overline{Q} and \mathbb{R} , respectively. The proof of the theorem is complete. \blacksquare

Theorem 2 *Let the conditions $f \in C(\overline{Q} \times \mathbb{R})$, $F \in C(\overline{Q})$, and $w \in C(\overline{Q})$ hold, and let the function f satisfy the Lipschitz condition with respect to the third variable, i.e., $|f(t, x, z_1) - f(t, x, z_2)| \leq k(t, x)|z_1 - z_2|$, where $k \in C(\overline{Q})$. Then there exists a unique solution of Eq. (3) in the space $C(\overline{Q})$.*

PROOF

We will prove the solvability of Eq. (1) using the Leray–Schauder fixed point principle. For

$$\mathcal{I}[u](t, x) = \int_0^t G(t, \tau) f(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), u(\tau, x + a(t - \tau))) d\tau, \quad u \in C(\Omega_{i,T}),$$

To prove the compactness of the operator K , it

The results of the article [2] let us write

brevity, we denote

$$G(t, \tau) = \frac{1}{(m - 1)!} \exp(-b(t - \tau))(t - \tau)^{m-1}, \\ G_K(t, x, \tau) = G(t, \tau)k(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)), \\ G_F(t, x, \tau) = G(t, \tau)f(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), 0).$$

1. *Compactness.* Let us prove that the operator $K: C(\Omega_{i,T}) \mapsto C(\Omega_{i,T})$ is compact, where $\Omega_{i,T} = \{(t, x) \mid 0 \leq t \leq T \wedge -i \leq x + at \leq i\}$. It is obvious that the operator K , defined by the formula (3), acts from the space $C(\Omega_{i,T})$ to the space $C(\Omega_{i,T})$ and is continuous. The operator $K: C(\Omega_{i,T}) \mapsto C(\Omega_{i,T})$ admits a representation $K = \mathcal{P} + \mathcal{I}$, where

$$\mathcal{P}[u](t, x) = w(t, x) + \int_0^t G(t, \tau) F(\tau, x \\ + a(t - \tau)) d\tau, \quad u \in C(\Omega_{i,T}),$$

and

suffices to prove the compactness of the operators

\mathcal{P} and \mathcal{I} . The compactness of the operator \mathcal{P} is obvious. So it remains to prove the compactness of the operator \mathcal{I} . Let us use the compactness criterion for operators in the space $C(\Omega_{i,T})$, i.e., the Arzelà–Ascoli theorem. We consider a

uniformly bounded set $M \subset C(\Omega_{i,T})$. It implies the existence of a real number $C_1 > 0$ such that $\|g\|_{C(\Omega_{i,T})} \leq C_1$ for any $g \in M$. The boundedness of a set $\mathcal{I}(M)$ follows from the following inequality:

$$\|\mathcal{I}[g]\|_{C(\Omega_{i,T})} = \sup_{(t,x) \in \Omega_{i,T}} \left| \frac{1}{(m-1)!} \int_0^t \exp(-b(t-\tau))(t-\tau)^{m-1} \right. \\ \left. \times f(\tau, x + a(t-\tau), g(\tau, x + a(t-\tau))) d\tau \right| \leq \begin{cases} M_F b^{-m}, & b \neq 0, \\ M_F T^m m^{-1}, & b = 0, \end{cases}$$

where $M_F = \|f\|_{C(\Omega_{i,T} \times [-C_1, C_1])}$. It remains to prove the equicontinuity of the set M . Let us fix

$\varepsilon > 0$ and $(t_1, x_1), (t_2, x_2) \in \Omega_{m,T}$, $t_1 \leq t_2$, so that $|t_1 - t_2| + |x_1 - x_2| \leq \varepsilon$, and calculate

$$|\mathcal{I}[g](t_1, x_2) - \mathcal{I}[g](t_2, x_2)| \leq \left| \int_0^{t_1} G(t, \tau) f(\tau, x_1 + a(t_1 - \tau)g(\tau, x_1 + a(t_1 - \tau))) d\tau \right. \\ \left. - \int_0^{t_2} G(t, \tau) f(\tau, x_2 + a(t_2 - \tau)g(\tau, x_2 + a(t_2 - \tau))) d\tau \right| \\ \leq \left| \int_0^{t_1} G_K(t_1, x_1, \tau) g(\tau, x_1 + a(t_1 - \tau)) d\tau - \int_0^{t_1} G_F(t_1, x_1, \tau) d\tau - \int_0^{t_2} G_K(t_2, x_2, \tau) g(\tau, x_2 \right. \\ \left. + a(t_2 - \tau)) d\tau + \int_0^{t_2} G_F(t_2, x_2, \tau) d\tau \right|.$$

Since the functions

$$I_f: \Omega_{i,T} \ni (t, x) \mapsto \int_0^t G_F(t, x, \tau) d\tau \in \mathbb{R}, I_k: \Omega_{i,T} \ni (t, x) \mapsto \int_0^t G_K(t, x, \tau) d\tau \in \mathbb{R},$$

are uniformly continuous, i.e., for every real number $\varepsilon > 0$ there exist real numbers $\delta_f(\varepsilon) > 0$ and $\delta_k(\varepsilon) > 0$ such that for every $(t_1, x_1), (t_2, x_2) \in \Omega_{i,T}$ with $|t_1 - t_2| + |x_1 - x_2| \leq \varepsilon$, we have $|I_f(t_1, x_1) - I_f(t_2, x_2)| \leq \delta_f(\varepsilon)$ and $|I_k(t_1, x_1) - I_k(t_2, x_2)| \leq \delta_k(\varepsilon)$. It implies

$$|\mathcal{I}[g](t_1, x_2) - \mathcal{I}[g](t_2, x_2)| \leq \delta_{I,M}(\varepsilon) := \delta_f(\varepsilon) + C_1 \delta_k(\varepsilon).$$

It proves the equicontinuity of the set M in the space $\Omega_{i,T}$. Hence, the operator $K: C(\Omega_{i,T}) \mapsto C(\Omega_{i,T})$ is compact.

2. *A priori estimates.* Let $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ and the function u_λ be a continuous solution of a

nonlinear Volterra integral equation

$$u_\lambda(t, x) = \lambda K[u_\lambda](t, x), \quad (t, x) \in \Omega_{i,T}. \quad (5)$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} |u_\lambda(t, x)| &= |\lambda K[u_\lambda](t, x)| \leq |\lambda w(t, x)| + \frac{\lambda}{(m-1)!} \int_0^t \exp(-b(t-\tau)) \\ &\quad \times (t-\tau)^{m-1} |f(\tau, x+a(t-\tau), u_\lambda(\tau, x+a(t-\tau)))| d\tau \\ &\leq C_w + \frac{1}{(m-1)!} \int_0^t \exp(-b(t-\tau)) (t-\tau)^{m-1} \left(f(\tau, x+a(t-\tau), \right. \\ &\quad \left. u_\lambda(\tau, x+a(t-\tau))) - f(\tau, x+a(t-\tau), 0) + f(\tau, x+a(t-\tau), 0) \right) d\tau \\ &\leq C_w + C_f + \frac{1}{(m-1)!} \int_0^t \exp(-b(t-\tau)) (t-\tau)^{m-1} k(\tau, x+a(t-\tau)) \times |u_\lambda(\tau, x+a(t-\tau))| d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \Omega_{i,T}, \end{aligned}$$

where $C_w = \|w\|_{C(\Omega_{i,T})}$ and

$$C_f = \sup_{(t,x) \in \Omega_{i,T}} \left| \frac{1}{(m-1)!} \int_0^t \exp(-b(t-\tau)) (t-\tau)^{m-1} f(\tau, x+a(t-\tau), 0) d\tau \right|.$$

Let us fix $x \in [-i, i]$ and denote $v(s) = |u_\lambda(s, x+a(t-s))|$. Then the function $v(s)$ satisfies the following inequality:

$$0 \leq v(t) \leq C_w + C_f + C_k \int_0^t G(t, \tau) v(\tau) d\tau, \quad t \in [0, T], \quad (6)$$

where $C_k = \|k\|_{C(\Omega_{i,T})}$. Applying the Grönwall inequality, we get

$$v(t) \leq (C_w + C_f) \exp\left(C_k \int_0^t G(t, \tau) d\tau\right), \quad t \in [0, T].$$

It implies an a priori estimate

$$\|u_\lambda\|_{C(\Omega_{i,T})} \leq C_a := (C_w + C_f) \sup_{(t,x) \in \Omega_{i,T}} \left| \exp\left(C_k \int_0^t G(t, \tau) d\tau\right) \right|, \quad (7)$$

where the constant C_a is independent of the solution u_λ .

3. *Local solvability.* For any value of the parameter $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ and for any continuous solution u_λ of Eq. (5) of Eq. (5) we have the a priori estimate (7) with the same positive constant C_a , which is independent of λ . Therefore,

by the Leray–Schauder theorem (see, e.g., [10]), under the assumptions of this theorem, Eq. (5) for $\lambda = 1$ has at least one solution $u \in C(\Omega_{i,T})$. Let us prove the uniqueness of the solution of Eq. (5) for $\lambda = 1$ by contradiction. Let Eq. (5) for $\lambda = 1$ has two solutions $u^{(1)}$ and $u^{(2)}$. Denote $U = u^{(1)} - u^{(2)}$. Then

$$U(t, x) = \int_0^t G(t, \tau) f(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), u^{(1)}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau))) d\tau - \int_0^t G(t, \tau) f(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), u^{(2)}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau))) d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \Omega_{i,T}. \quad (8)$$

The function U is continuous, and hence $|U(t, x)| \leq M_U$ under the condition $(t, x) \in \Omega_{i,T}$,

where M_U is some constant. It follows from (8) with allowance for the Lipschitz condition that

$$U(t, x) \leq \int_0^t G_K(t, x, \tau) U(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)) d\tau \leq \int_0^t \mathcal{K} M_U d\tau = \mathcal{K} M_U t, \quad (t, x) \in \Omega_{i,T},$$

where $\mathcal{K} = \|G_K\|_{C(\Omega_{i,T} \times [0, T])}$. By induction, we arrive at the estimate

$$U(t, x) \leq \frac{\mathcal{K}^l M_U t^l}{m!}$$

for each positive integer l and any pair (t, x) in $\Omega_{i,T}$. It follows that $U \equiv 0$ on the set $\Omega_{i,T}$. Thus, we have proved the existence of a unique continuous solution of Eq. (5) for $\lambda = 1$.

4. *Global solvability.* Now we claim that the function $u = \lim_{j \rightarrow \infty} u^{(j)}$ is a continuous solution of Eq. (3), where $u^{(j)}$ is a solution of the integral equation $u^{(j)}(t, x) = K[u^{(j)}](t, x)$ in the space $C(\Omega_{j,T})$ (outside the set $\Omega_{j,T}$ we can assume that the functions $u^{(j)}$ are continued in a continuous way), where $j \in \mathbb{N}$. From the above arguments and the finite propagation speed [11],

it is easy to see that for any $k \in \mathbb{N}$ the equality $(u^{(j+k)} - u^{(j)})|_{\Omega_{j,T}} \equiv 0$ holds. Since $\bigcup_{j=1}^{\infty} \Omega_{j,T}$, the topology of the Fréchet space $C(\overline{Q})$ can be given by a countable family of seminorms $p_j(w) = \|w\|_{C(\Omega_{j,T})}$. The sequence $(u^{(j)})$ is the Cauchy sequence with respect to each of these seminorms p_k , $k \in \mathbb{N}$. So the function u is well-defined. Because of $u|_{\Omega_{j,T}} = u^{(j)}|_{\Omega_{j,T}}$, we have

$$u(t, x) = u^{(j)}(t, x) = K[u^{(j)}](t, x) = K[u](t, x),$$

where $(t, x) \in \Omega_{j,T}$. Due to the arbitrariness of $(t, x) \in \overline{Q}$, we get $u = K[u]$ in the space $C(\overline{Q})$. The uniqueness of the continuous solution u of Eq. (3) can be proved in a similar way as the previous item of this proof. The theorem is

proved. ■

Remark 1 One can formulate local variants of Theorems 1 and 2, where we replace the set Q with $\Omega = \{(t, x) \mid 0 < t < T \wedge x_0 < x + at < x_1\}$, where $T > 0$, $-\infty < x_0 < x_1 < +\infty$, and the condition $\varphi \in C^{2m-j-1}(\mathbb{R})$ with $\varphi \in C^{2m-j-1}([x_0, x_1])$

Remark 2 In Remark 1, we set Ω in such a way that the initial data given on the interval $[x_0, x_1]$ uniquely determine the solution on Ω , i.e., Ω is the “truncated” domain of dependence of the interval $[x_0, x_1]$ (the domain of dependence of the interval $[x_0, x_1]$ is a set $\{(t, x) \mid t > 0 \wedge x_0 < x + at < x_1\}$). This question is discussed in more detail in the book [11].

It follows from Theorems 1 and 2 that the Cauchy problem (1), (2) admits a unique classical solution under sufficient smoothness conditions and the Lipschitz condition, which is imposed on the nonlinearity.

5. Existence and uniqueness theorem for Lipschitz nonlinearities

Theorem 3 Let the conditions $f \in C^{0,m,m}(\overline{Q} \times \mathbb{R})$, $F \in C^{0,m,m}(\overline{Q})$, $\varphi^{(j)} \in C^{2m-j-1}(\mathbb{R})$ ($j = 0, \dots, m - 1$) be satisfied, and let the function

$$U(t, x) = \int_0^t G(t, \tau) (f(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), u^{(1)}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)) - f(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), u^{(2)}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)))) d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \overline{\Omega}. \quad (9)$$

Taking the absolute value from both sides of the equality (9) and applying the estimate $|G(t, \tau)| \leq$

f satisfy the Lipschitz condition with respect to the third variable, i.e., $|f(t, x, z_1) - f(t, x, z_2)| \leq k(t, x)|z_1 - z_2|$, where $k \in C(\overline{Q})$. Then the Cauchy problem (1), (2) has a unique solution u in the class $C^m(\overline{Q})$.

PROOF

The **proof** follows from Theorems 1 and 2. ■

6. Uniqueness theorem for a wide class of nonlinearities

Before proceeding to the consideration of non-Lipschitz nonlinearities, we formulate the following uniqueness theorem.

Theorem 4 Let the conditions $f \in C(\overline{\Omega} \times \mathbb{R})$, $\frac{\partial f}{\partial u}(\bullet_1, \bullet_2, u = \bullet_3) \in C(\overline{\Omega} \times \mathbb{R})$, $F \in C(\overline{\Omega})$, $\varphi^{(j)} \in C^{2m-j-1}(\mathbb{R})$, $j = 0, \dots, m - 1$ be satisfied. Then the Cauchy problem (1), (2) has at most one classical solution defined on the set Ω , where $\Omega = \{(t, x) \mid 0 < t < T \wedge x_0 < x + at < x_1\}$, where $0 < T \leq +\infty$, $-\infty \leq x_0 < x_1 \leq +\infty$.

PROOF

By contradiction. Let Eq. (5) for $\lambda = 1$ has two solutions $u^{(1)}$ and $u^{(2)}$. Denote $U = u^{(1)} - u^{(2)}$. Then

$M_G = \|G\|_{[0,T] \times [0,T]}$ for $(t, \tau) \in \overline{\Omega}$, we get

$$|U(t, x)| \leq M_G \int_0^t |f(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), u^{(1)}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)) - f(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), u^{(2)}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)))| d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \bar{\Omega}.$$

Using the mean value theorem for the function $z \mapsto f(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), z)$, we get

$$|U(t, x)| \leq M_G \int_0^t |U(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)) \frac{\partial f}{\partial u}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau), u = \theta u^{(1)}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)) + (1 - \theta)u^{(2)}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)))| d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \bar{\Omega}.$$

for some real number $\theta \in [0, 1]$. Due to the continuity, there is an estimate

$$|\theta u^{(1)}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau)) + (1 - \theta)u^{(2)}(\tau, x + a(t - \tau))| \leq M_U^{(1)} := \|u^{(1)}\|_{C(\bar{\Omega})} + \|u^{(2)}\|_{C(\bar{\Omega})}.$$

It leads to

$$|U(t, x)| \leq M_f \int_0^t |U(\tau, x + a(t - \tau))| d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \bar{\Omega}, \tag{10}$$

where

$$M_f = M_G \left\| \frac{\partial f}{\partial u}(\bullet_1, \bullet_2, u = \bullet_3) \right\|_{C(\bar{\Omega} \times [-M_U^{(1)}, M_U^{(1)}])}.$$

For fixed x we denote $V(s) = |U(s, x + a(t - s))|$ and rewrite (10) as

$$0 \leq V(t) \leq M_f \int_0^t V(\tau) d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \bar{\Omega}.$$

By the Grönwall's inequality, we obtain $V(t) = 0$ for any $t \in [0, T]$. And virtue of the arbitrariness of x , we get $U \equiv 0$ on the set Ω . The theorem is proved.

Remark 3 Since the mean value theorem does not require continuity of the derivative, it requires the existence of the derivative everywhere, the condition

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial u}(\bullet_1, \bullet_2, u = \bullet_3) \in C(\bar{\Omega} \times \mathbb{R})$$

of the Theorem 4 can be weakened. For example, we can assume that the derivative $\frac{\partial f}{\partial u}(\bullet_1, \bullet_2, u = \bullet_3)$ exists and belongs to the class $\mathcal{B}_{\text{loc}}(\bar{\Omega} \times \mathbb{R})$.

Following [37], we make the following assertion, where the partial derivative $\frac{\partial f}{\partial u}(\bullet_1, \bullet_2, u = \bullet_3)$ may have singularities.

Assertion 1 In Theorem 4 we can assume that the derivative $\frac{\partial f}{\partial u}(\bullet_1, \bullet_2, u = \bullet_3)$ exists and

satisfies the following condition:

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial u}(t, x, u) \leq \alpha(t, x)\psi(|u|),$$

instead of

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial u}(\bullet_1, \bullet_2, u = \bullet_3) \in C(\bar{\Omega} \times \mathbb{R}),$$

where ψ is positive function defined on the range $[0, \infty)$ and belongs to the class $\mathcal{B}_{\text{loc}}([0, \infty))$, the

function $s \mapsto \alpha(s, x + a(t - s))$ belongs to the class $L^p_{\text{loc}}([0, T])$, where $p > 1$, for any fixed $x \in [x_1, x_2]$.

PROOF

In this state, we first consider that T is finite. Instead of the estimate (10) we now have

$$|U(t, x)| \leq M_\psi \int_0^t |U(\tau, x + a(t - \tau))\alpha(\tau, x + a(t - \tau))| d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \bar{\Omega}, \quad (11)$$

where $M_\psi = M_G \|\psi\|_{C([0, M_U^{(1)}])}$. Again for fixed x we denote $V(s) = |U(s, x + a(t - s))|$ and $\beta(s) = |\alpha(s, x + a(t - s))|$ and rewrite (10) as

$$0 \leq V(t) \leq M_\psi \int_0^t \beta(\tau)V(\tau) d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \bar{\Omega}.$$

Hölder's inequality gives

$$V(t) \leq M_\psi \|\beta\|_{L^p([0, T])} \left(\int_0^t V^q(\tau) d\tau \right)^{1/q}, \quad (t, x) \in \bar{\Omega},$$

where $1/q + 1/p = 1$. By the well-known generalization of the Grönwall–Bellman inequality given by Willett and Wong [38], we obtain $V(t) = 0$ for any $t \in [0, T]$. And due to the arbitrariness of x , we get $U \equiv 0$ on the set Ω .

If $T = \infty$, then we apply the above argument sequentially for $T = 1, 2, \dots$ and conclude that the $U \equiv 0$ on any set of the form $\Omega \cap \{(t, x) \mid t \in [0, j]\}$ for any positive integer j . Since in this case $\bigcup_{j=1}^\infty \Omega \cap \{(t, x) \mid t \in [0, j]\} = \Omega$, we get $U \equiv 0$ on the set Ω . The state is proven. ■

Let us consider an example of a violation of the conditions of the assertions formulated in this section.

Example 3. Let's consider the function f having the form

$$f(t, x, u) = u^\alpha, \quad 0 < \alpha < 1. \quad (12)$$

and set

$$b = 0, \quad F \equiv 0, \quad \varphi^{(j)} \equiv 0, \quad j = 0, \dots, n - 1. \quad (13)$$

It is easy to see that the initial value problem (1), (2), (12), (13) has the trivial solution $u \equiv 0$. To find non-trivial solutions of the problem (1), (2), (12), (13) consider the ansatz

$$u(t, x) = u(t) = \beta t^\gamma \quad (14)$$

where β and γ are some real numbers. Substituting ansatz (14) into Eq. (1), we obtain the relation

$$t^{\gamma-n} \beta \text{FactorialPower}(\gamma, n) = \beta^\alpha t^{\alpha\gamma} \quad (15)$$

where we have used the notation

$$\text{FactorialPower}(x, n) = \frac{\Gamma(x + 1)}{\Gamma(x + 1 - n)},$$

where Γ is the gamma function. The representation (15) leads to the system of equations

$$\gamma - n = \gamma\alpha, \quad \beta \text{FactorialPower}(\gamma, n) = \beta^\alpha,$$

which has the solution

$$\beta = \left(\text{FactorialPower} \left(\frac{n}{1-\alpha}, n \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}}, \quad (16)$$

$$\gamma = \frac{n}{1-\alpha}.$$

Substituting (16) into (14), we get the function

$$u_p(t, x) = \left(\text{FactorialPower} \left(\frac{n}{1-\alpha}, n \right) \right)^{\frac{1}{1-\alpha}} t^{\frac{n}{1-\alpha}}. \quad (17)$$

It is easy to see that the function (17) satisfies Eq. (1) and the initial conditions (2). Thus, we have constructed one nontrivial solution of the problem (1) – (2), (12), (13), which is determined by the formula (17). Moreover, one can easily show that the ‘glued’ solution

$$u_{p;s}(t, x) = \begin{cases} 0, & t \in [0, s), \\ u_p(t-s, x), & t \in [s, +\infty), \end{cases}$$

with parameter $s > 0$ also satisfies the problem (1) – (2), (12), (13). Thus, we have constructed the infinite set of nontrivial classical solutions of the problem (1) – (2), (12), (13).

We note that in the problem (1) – (2), (12), (13) the nonlinearity $u \mapsto u^\alpha$ is not differentiable function on the set \mathbb{R} , which makes it impossible to apply the mean value theorem. It violates the statements of Theorem 4,

Remark 3, and Assertion 1. This example is also significant in that it follows from it that the Lipschitz condition $|f(t, x, z_1) - f(t, x, z_2)| \leq k(t, x)|z_1 - z_2|$ cannot be weakened to a Hölder condition $|f(t, x, z_1) - f(t, x, z_2)| \leq k(t, x)|z_1 - z_2|^\lambda$ with the exponent $\lambda \in (0, 1)$ and at the same time preserving the existence and uniqueness of the Cauchy problem (1) – (2).

7. Reduction to the Cauchy problem for an ordinary differential equation

Making the linear nondegenerate change of independent variables

$$\tau = t, \quad \xi = x + at, \quad (18)$$

and denoting

$$u(t, x) = v(\tau, \xi), \quad (19)$$

we obtain the new differential equation

$$\left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \tau} + b \right)^m v(\tau, \xi) = \Phi(\tau, \xi, v(\tau, \xi)), \quad (20)$$

where $\Phi(\tau, \xi, v) = F(\tau, \xi - a\tau) + f(\tau, \xi - a\tau, v)$. The initial conditions for the function v can be computed using the Faà di Bruno’s formula or recursively using the chain rule, and they have the form

$$\tilde{\varphi}^{(0)}(\xi) = v(0, \xi) = u(0, x = \xi) = \varphi^{(0)}(\xi),$$

$$\tilde{\varphi}^{(i)}(\xi) = \frac{\partial^i v}{\partial \tau^i}(0, \xi) = \sum_{j=0}^i \binom{i}{j} (-a)^{i-j} D^{i-j} \varphi_j(\xi), \quad i = 1, \dots, m-1. \quad (21)$$

Moreover, the smoothness of the ‘new’ initial conditions is not worse than the ‘old’ ones, in the sense that $\varphi^{(j)} \in C^{l-j}(\Omega)$ if and only if $\tilde{\varphi}^{(j)} \in C^{l-j}(\Omega)$, where $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}$, $l \in \mathbb{N} \cap [m, \infty)$, and $j \in 0, \dots, m-1$. It is also easy to see that $\Phi \in C^{0,m,m}(\Omega)$ if and only if $F \in C^{0,m}(\Omega)$ and $f \in C^{0,m,m}(\Omega)$.

Now Eq. (20) with the conditions (21) can be considered as the Cauchy problem for an ordinary differential equation with the parameter ξ , i.e.,

$$(D + b)^m v_\xi(\tau) = \Phi(\tau, \xi, v_\xi(\tau)), \quad (22)$$

$$D^j v_\xi(0) = \tilde{\varphi}^{(j)}(\xi), \quad j = 0, \dots, m. \quad (23)$$

We can say that the problems (1) – (2) and (22) – (23) are the same in the sense that the problem (1) – (2) is posed in the Eulerian coordinates (t, x) , and the problem (22) – (23) is written in the Lagrangian coordinates (τ, ξ) .

Our goal is to construct solutions to the Cauchy problem (1), (2) as solutions to the Cauchy problem (22), (23). Due to the change

of variables (18) and the notation (19), we have to impose such smoothness conditions on the functions Φ and $\tilde{\varphi}^{(j)}$ ($j = 0, \dots, m$) so that the function $(\tau, \xi) \mapsto v(\tau, \xi) = v_\xi(\tau)$ has all partial derivatives up to the order m inclusive. To study these properties, let us solve Eq. (20) for $D^m v_\xi$ and rewrite it in the explicit form

$$D^m v_\xi(\tau) = \tilde{\Phi}(\tau, \xi, v_\xi(\tau), Dv_\xi(\tau), D^2 v_\xi(\tau), \dots, D^{m-1} v_\xi(\tau)) = \Phi(\tau, \xi, v_\xi(\tau)) - \sum_{i=1}^m \binom{m}{i} b^{n-i} D^i v_\xi(\tau) \tag{24}$$

For further study, it is convenient to write Eq. (24) in the form of a system

$$\begin{aligned} Dv_\xi^{(m)}(\tau) &= \tilde{\Phi}(\tau, \xi, v_\xi^{(1)}(\tau), v_\xi^{(2)}(\tau), \dots, v_\xi^{(m)}(\tau)), \\ Dv_\xi^{(j)}(\tau) &= v_\xi^{(j+1)}(\tau), \quad j = 1, \dots, m-1. \end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

In this case, the initial conditions have the form

$$v_\xi^{(j)}(0) = \tilde{\varphi}^{(j-1)}(\xi), \quad j = 1, \dots, m. \tag{26}$$

For the Cauchy problem (25), (26) there is a theorem about the differentiability of solutions with respect to the parameter and initial data [39] (Ch. 3, § 8, Corollary 8.3). It states that the solution $v_\xi^{(j)}$ ($j = 1, \dots, m$) of the Cauchy problem (25), (26) has continuous derivatives $\partial_\xi^p v_\xi^{(j)}$ ($j = 1, \dots, m$) if the functions $\tilde{\varphi}^{(j)}$ ($j = 0, \dots, m-1$) have derivatives of the order p and the function Φ has derivatives of the order p with respect to ξ and v_ξ (the last argument). It follows immediately from this that the function $[0, T] \times [x_1, x_2] \ni (\tau, \xi) \mapsto v_\xi(\tau) \in \mathbb{R}$, where v_ξ is a classical solution of the problem (25), (26), belongs to the class $C^m([0, T] \times [x_1, x_2])$ if, for example, $\Phi \in C^{0,m,m}([0, T] \times [x_1, x_2] \times \mathbb{R})$ and $\tilde{\varphi} \in C^{2m-j-1}([x_1, x_2])$. Thus, under the smoothness conditions of $F \in C^{0,m}([0, T] \times [x_1, x_2])$, $f \in C^{0,m,m}([0, T] \times [x_1, x_2] \times \mathbb{R})$ and $\varphi \in C^{2m-j-1}([x_1, x_2])$, the classical solution u

of the original Cauchy problem (1), (2) can be obtained as the classical solution v_ξ of the Cauchy problem (22), (23) for the ordinary differential equation with the parameter ξ .

Example 4. Consider the problem (1), (2), where $n = 2$, $b = 0$, $f(t, x, u) = -\exp(x + at)u$, and $F \equiv 0$. The corresponding ordinary differential equation for the function v_ξ has the form

$$D^2 v_\xi(\tau) + \exp(\xi)v_\xi(\tau) = 0.$$

It has the general solution

$$\begin{aligned} v_\xi(\tau) &= C_1(\xi) \sin\left(\exp\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\right)\tau\right) \\ &+ C_2(\xi) \cos\left(\exp\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\right)\tau\right), \end{aligned}$$

where the values $C_1(\xi)$ and $C_2(\xi)$ are determined from the initial conditions

$$\begin{aligned} v_\xi(0) &= C_2(\xi) = \tilde{\varphi}^{(0)}(\xi) = \varphi^{(0)}(\xi), \\ Dv_\xi(0) &= \exp\left(\frac{\xi}{2}\right) C_1(\xi) = \tilde{\varphi}^{(1)}(\xi) \\ &= \varphi^{(1)}(\xi) - aD\varphi^{(0)}(\xi). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, the solution of the Cauchy problem (1), (2) in this example has the form

$$u(t, x) = \exp\left(-\frac{x + at}{2}\right) \left(\varphi^{(1)}(x + at) - aD\varphi^{(0)}(x + at) \right) \times \sin\left(\exp\left(\frac{x + at}{2}\right) t\right) + \varphi^{(0)}(x + at) \cos\left(\exp\left(\frac{x + at}{2}\right) t\right).$$

Thus, within the framework of this method, it is possible to construct solutions of the Cauchy problem (1), (2) in quadratures.

8. Mild solution

Let us simplify Eq. (22). We use the following ansatz

$$v_\xi(\tau) = w_\xi(\tau) \exp(-b\tau) \tag{27}$$

Substituting (27) into (22), we obtain the equation

$$D^m w_\xi(\tau) = \tilde{\Phi}(\tau, \xi, w_\xi(\tau) \exp(-b\tau)) \exp(b\tau), \tag{28}$$

with the Cauchy conditions

$$w_\xi(0) = \psi_0(\xi) = \tilde{\varphi}^{(0)}(\xi) \exp(b\tau), \quad D^i w_\xi(0) = \psi_i(\xi) = \sum_{j=0}^i \binom{i}{j} b^j \tilde{\varphi}^{(i-j)}(\xi), \quad i = 1, \dots, m - 1. \tag{29}$$

Now we can use the theory of generalized solutions for ordinary differential equations to construct generalized solutions of the Cauchy problem (1), (2).

Again, we note that the smoothness of the ‘new’ initial conditions is not worse than the ‘old’

ones, in the sense that $\psi^{(j)} \in C^{l-j}(\Omega)$ if and only if $\tilde{\varphi}^{(j)} \in C^{l-j}(\Omega)$, where $\Omega \subseteq \mathbb{R}$, $l \geq m - 1$, and $j \in 0, \dots, m - 1$.

The classical and mild solutions of the problem (28), (29) can be represented as [40]

$$w_\xi(\tau) = \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \frac{\psi_i(\xi) \tau^i}{i!} + \frac{1}{(m-1)!} \int_0^\tau \tilde{\Phi}(\tau_1, \xi, w_\xi(\tau_1) \exp(-b\tau_1)) \exp(-b\tau_1) (\tau - \tau_1)^{m-1} d\tau_1.$$

Returning to the original variables, we get

$$u(t, x) = \sum_{i=0}^{m-1} \frac{\psi_i(x + at) \exp(-bt)t^i}{i!} + \frac{1}{(m-1)!} \int_0^t \exp(-b(t-\tau))(t-\tau)^{m-1} \times (F(\tau, x + a(t-\tau)) - f(\tau, x + a(t-\tau), u(\tau, x + a(t-\tau)))) d\tau, \quad (t, x) \in \bar{Q}. \quad (30)$$

i. e., we have determined the function w in the expression (3).

We can use Eq. (30) to define a mild solution of the Cauchy problem (1), (2).

Definition 1 *The function u is a mild solution of the Cauchy problem (1), (2) if it is a solution of Eq. (30).*

We can state the existence theorem for a mild solution.

Theorem 5 *Let the conditions $f \in C(\bar{Q} \times \mathbb{R})$, $F \in C(\bar{Q})$, $\varphi^{(j)} \in C^{m-j-1}(\mathbb{R})$ ($j = 0, \dots, m-1$) be satisfied, and let the function f satisfy the Lipschitz condition with respect to the third variable, i.e., $|f(t, x, z_1) - f(t, x, z_2)| \leq k(t, x)|z_1 - z_2|$, where $k \in C(\bar{Q})$. Then the Cauchy problem (1), (2) has a unique mild solution u in the class $C(\bar{Q})$.*

PROOF

The **proof** follows from Theorem 2. ■

Also, we can formulate the following uniqueness theorem for a mild solution.

Theorem 6 *Let the conditions $f \in C(\bar{\Omega} \times \mathbb{R})$, $\frac{\partial f}{\partial u}(\bullet_1, \bullet_2, u = \bullet_3) \in C(\bar{\Omega} \times \mathbb{R})$, $F \in C(\bar{\Omega})$, $\varphi^{(j)} \in C^{m-j-1}(\mathbb{R})$, $j = 0, \dots, m-1$ be satisfied. Then the Cauchy problem (1), (2) has at most one mild solution defined on the set Ω , where $\Omega = \{(t, x) \mid 0 < t < T \wedge x_0 < x + at < x_1\}$, where $0 < T \leq +\infty$, $-\infty \leq x_0 < x_1 \leq +\infty$.*

PROOF

The **proof** follows from the proof of Theorem 4. ■

9. Second-order equation

In this section, we use the method of reduction to an ordinary differential equation to find solutions to the Cauchy problem (1), (2) with the non-Lipschitz nonlinearities. Let us begin by considering Eq. (1) in the following case

$$m = 2, \quad b = 0, \quad f(t, x, u) = -\alpha(t, x)f(u). \quad (31)$$

The corresponding ordinary differential equation for the function v_ξ has the form

$$D^2 v_\xi(\tau) + \alpha_\xi(\tau)f(v_\xi(\tau)) = F_\xi(\tau), \quad (32)$$

where $\alpha_\xi(\tau) = \alpha(\tau, \xi - a\tau)$, $F_\xi(\tau) = F_\xi(\tau, \xi - a\tau)$. And the initial conditions for Eq. (32) are

$$v_\xi(0) = \tilde{\varphi}^{(0)}(\xi) = \varphi^{(0)}(\xi), \\ Dv_\xi(0) = \tilde{\varphi}^{(1)}(\xi) = \varphi^{(1)}(\xi) - aD\varphi^{(0)}(\xi). \quad (33)$$

We denote $G(z) := \int_0^z f(\eta) d\eta$. It is known [41]

that if

$$\alpha_\xi(\tau) > 0, \quad D\alpha_\xi(\tau) \leq 0 \text{ for all } \tau \in [0, \infty) \text{ and } \xi \in \mathbb{R}, \\ G(z) > 0 \text{ for } z \neq 0, \quad G(z) \rightarrow \infty \text{ as } |z| \rightarrow \infty, \quad (34)$$

holds, then the initial value problem (32), (33) has a solution defined on $[0, +\infty)$. Moreover, if $F_\xi(\tau) \equiv 0$, then the first condition $D\alpha_\xi(\tau) \geq 0$ for all $\tau \geq 0$ in (34) can be dropped. The uniqueness is proved as usual using the mean value theorem. It allows us to state the results.

Theorem 7 *The Cauchy problem*

$$(\partial_t - a\partial_x)^2 u(t, x) + \alpha(t, x)f(u(t, x)) = F(t, x), \\ (t, x) \in Q,$$

$$u(0, x) = \varphi^{(0)}(x), \quad \partial_t u(0, x) = \varphi^{(1)}(x), \quad x \in \mathbb{R},$$

has a unique solution in the class $C^2(\bar{Q})$, if the

smoothness conditions

$$f \in C^2(\mathbb{R}), \alpha \in C^2(\overline{Q}), F \in C^{0,2}(\overline{Q}),$$

$$\varphi^{(0)} \in C^3(\mathbb{R}), \varphi^{(1)} \in C^2(\mathbb{R}),$$

the sign conditions

$$\alpha(t, x) > 0 \text{ for all } (t, x) \in \overline{Q},$$

$$\int_0^z f(\eta) d\eta > 0 \text{ for } z \neq 0,$$

$$\int_0^z f(\eta) d\eta \rightarrow \infty \text{ as } |z| \rightarrow \infty,$$

and one of the following conditions

1. $F(t, x) = 0$ for all $(t, x) \in \overline{Q}$;
2. $(\partial_t - a\partial_x)\alpha(t, x) \leq 0$ for all $(t, x) \in \overline{Q}$;

hold.

PROOF

The **proof** of Theorem 7 follows from the above argument. ■

Note in particular that the sign condition for the function f specified in Theorem 7 holds for functions of polynomial growth such as $z \mapsto z^{2k+1}$, $k = 0, 1, \dots$, and for the functions of the form $z \mapsto f_0(z) \operatorname{sign}(z)$, where $f_0 > 0$ and $f_0(z) \rightarrow \infty$ as $|z| \rightarrow \infty$.

The results of the paper [41] allow us to consider also the case of nonnegative b . Indeed,

$$(\partial_t - a\partial_x + b)^2 u(t, x) + \alpha(x + at)f(u(t, x)) = F(t, x), \quad (t, x) \in Q, \quad u(0, x) = \varphi^{(0)}(x),$$

$$\partial_t u(0, x) = \varphi^{(1)}(x), \quad x \in \mathbb{R},$$

has a unique solution in the class $C^2(\overline{Q})$, if the

let

$$m = 2, \quad f(t, x, u) = -\alpha(x + at)f(u). \quad (35)$$

The corresponding ordinary differential equation for the function v_ξ takes the form

$$D^2 v_\xi(\tau) + 2bDv_\xi(\tau) + b^2 v + \alpha_\xi f(v_\xi(\tau)) = F_\xi(\tau). \quad (36)$$

where $\alpha_\xi = \alpha(\xi)$, $F_\xi(\tau) = F_\xi(\tau, \xi - a\tau)$. The initial conditions for Eq. (36) are (33) as in the previous case. We denote

$$G^{(1)}(z) := \int_0^z (b^2 \eta + \alpha_\xi f(\eta)) d\eta$$

$$= \frac{b^2 z^2}{2} + \alpha_\xi \int_0^z f(\eta) d\eta.$$

As the paper [41] says, if

$$b > 0, \alpha_\xi > 0, G^{(1)}(z) > 0 \text{ for } z \neq 0,$$

$$G^{(1)}(z) \rightarrow \infty \text{ as } |z| \rightarrow \infty, \quad (37)$$

holds, then the initial value problem (32), (33) has a solution defined on $[0, +\infty)$. The uniqueness is proved as in the previous case using the mean value theorem. It allows us to formulate the following statement.

Theorem 8 *The Cauchy problem*

smoothness conditions

$f \in C^2(\mathbb{R}), \quad \alpha \in C^2(\mathbb{R}), \quad F \in C^{0,2}(\overline{Q}), \quad \varphi^{(0)} \in C^3(\mathbb{R}), \quad \varphi^{(1)} \in C^2(\mathbb{R}),$
and the sign conditions

$$\forall (t, x) \in \overline{Q}: b > 0, \alpha(x + at) > 0, \quad \forall (t, x) \in \overline{Q}: \frac{b^2 z^2}{2} + \alpha(x + at) \int_0^z f(\eta) d\eta > 0 \text{ for } z \neq 0,$$

$$\forall (t, x) \in \overline{Q}: \frac{b^2 z^2}{2} + \alpha(x + at) \int_0^z f(\eta) d\eta \rightarrow \infty \text{ as } |z| \rightarrow \infty,$$

hold.

PROOF

The **proof** of Theorem 8 follows from the above argument. ■

10. Positive nonlinearities

Let us now study the Cauchy problem (1), (2) when the nonlinearity has the form $f(t, x, z) = -\alpha(x + at)f(u)$, the functions $\varphi^{(j)}$ ($j = 0, \dots, n$) are identically zero, the right side F of Eq. (1) is identically zero, and b is zero. Unlike the previous two cases, we now assume that $m \geq 2$. So, we have the ordinary differential equation for the function v_ξ

$$D^m v_\xi(\tau) = g(v_\xi(\tau)) := -\alpha_\xi f(v_\xi(\tau)), \quad (38)$$

where $\alpha_\xi = \alpha(\xi)$. Eq. (38) is equipped with the initial conditions

$$D^j v_\xi(0) = 0, \quad j = 0, \dots, m - 1. \quad (39)$$

Suppose g is nondecreasing, nonnegative, and continuously differentiable on the set \mathbb{R} . According to the Picard's existence and

uniqueness theorem [39], the problem (38), (39) has a unique classical solution defined on the interval $[0, T)$ for some $T > 0$. We want to find conditions under which this solution is determined on the set $[0, +\infty)$, i.e., it does not blow up. It is obvious that if $g(0) = 0$, then this solution is trivial, and it is defined on the nonnegative half-line $[0, +\infty)$. But what can we say if $g(0) \neq 0$? It turns out that the solution v_ξ is positive, since the necessary and sufficient condition for the existence of a positive solution is satisfied [42]. This fact needs to be proved. Indeed, let us check these conditions given in the paper [42]:

1. The condition (1.3) of [42] is satisfied: $g \in C^1(\mathbb{R})$, and $g(x) \geq 0$ for all $x \in \mathbb{R}$.
2. The condition (1.4) of [42] is satisfied: the function $s \mapsto s^\beta g(s)$ is bounded as $s \rightarrow 0+$ for $\beta = 0$.
3. The condition (1.6) of [42] is satisfied:

$$\int_0^1 g(s) s^{-(m-2)/(m-1)} ds \leq \|g\|_{C([0,1])} \int_0^1 s^{-(m-2)/(m-1)} ds = \|g\|_{C([0,1])} (m-1) < \infty.$$

4. The condition $g \in K^*$ of [42] is satisfied,

since $g^* \equiv g$, and hence $G^*/G \equiv 1 < \infty$.

5. The condition (1.7) of [42] is satisfied. In fact, the function ϕ , defined by the formula (1.8) of the paper [42], satisfies the estimate $\phi(x) = \Theta(x^{m-2+1/m})$ as $x \rightarrow 0$, where Θ is big theta. So, $(\phi(x))^{-1/(m-1)} = \Theta(x^{-1+1/m})$ as $x \rightarrow 0$, and the integral $\int_0^\delta (\phi(x))^{-1/(m-1)} dx$ converges.

Note that this solution v_ξ does not blow up if $\int_0^{+\infty} (\phi(x))^{-1/(m-1)} dx = \infty$ [42]. It allows us to formulate the following assertion.

Theorem 9 *Suppose $m \geq 2$. The Cauchy problem*

$$\begin{aligned} (\partial_t - a\partial_x)^m u(t, x) + \alpha(x + at)f(u(t, x)) &= 0, \\ (t, x) &\in Q, \\ \partial_t^j u(0, x) &= 0, \quad j = 0, \dots, m - 1, \quad x \in \mathbb{R} \end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

has a unique nontrivial solution in the class $C^m(\bar{Q})$, if the smoothness conditions

$$f \in C^m(\mathbb{R}), \quad \alpha \in C^m(\mathbb{R}), \tag{41}$$

the sign conditions

$$\begin{aligned} \forall (t, x) \in \bar{Q}: \quad \alpha(x + at)f(0) &< 0, \\ \alpha(x + at)f(z_1) &\leq \alpha(x + at)f(z_2), \text{ for all } z_1 > z_2, \\ \text{where } z_1, z_2 &\in [0, +\infty). \end{aligned} \tag{42}$$

hold, and the integral

$$\int_0^\infty p^{\frac{2-m}{m^2-m}} \left\{ \int_0^p -\alpha(x + at)f(s)(p - s)^{m-2} s^{-\frac{m-2}{m-1}} ds \right\}^{-\frac{1}{m}} dp \tag{43}$$

diverges for all $(t, x) \in \bar{Q}$.

PROOF

The **proof** of Theorem 9 follows from the above argument and results of the paper [42]. ■

Corollary 1 *If under the conditions of Theorem 9 the integral (43) converges, then the solution of the Cauchy problem (40) blows up.*

Using comparison theorems, one can establish the blow-up of a solution in finite time for more general Cauchy problems of the form (1), (2).

11. Conclusions

In the present paper, we have obtained sufficient conditions under which a unique classical solution of the Cauchy problem for the semilinear nonstrictly hyperbolic partial differential equation exists. We have constructed the solution in an implicit analytical form. We have also shown the method for finding the solution in quadratures for some cases of the considered equation.

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